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Enabling interoperable distributed ledger technology with legacy platforms for enterprise digitalization

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ABSTRACT

Presently to achieve enterprise digitalization technologies such as Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) has now been deployed to support digital services provided by enterprises. But several challenges in DLTs remain to be addressed, including the interoperability, standardization, and integration. Therefore, this study provides theoretical and practical understanding of DLT interoperability and identified the factors that influence the interoperability of DLTs. Also, an architecture is designed to show how interoperability can be achieved in DLTs and legacy systems supported by Application Programming Interface (API). A case study is presented to illustrate the applicability of the architecture to support a digital energy marketplace.

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1. Introduction

Distributed ledger technology (DLT) is believed to be an enabling infrastructure for enterprise processes and systems (Belchior et al. 2021; Chen et al. 2020). It allows enterprises to achieve digital transformation of their current business models by eliminating intermediaries, decreasing costs and enhancing trustworthiness among partners, thus enabling a new trend of decentralised platform-based services (Asante et al. 2021; Lima 2018; Lohachab et al. 2021). Findings from the literature suggest that DLTs such as Ethereum, Corda, Ripple, Hyperledger Fabric, blockchain, IOTA Tangle, etc. propose great potential to support the exchange of immutable and secure data across different stakeholders (Anthony Jnr 2023c; Hardjono, Lipton, and Pentland 2019; Hawig et al. 2019). DLT offers the next-generation decentralised internet of value, where assets and digital transactions are authenticated and maintained in a distributed ledger creating a new model for enterprise digitalisation (Lima 2018; Madine et al. 2021). DLTs are now becoming the underlying infrastructure for digital transformation creating a new trend of decentralised platforms and applications, referred to as dApps (Carter, Shahriar, and Sneha 2019; Lima 2018), which will be deployed to replace most of the centralised cloud-based systems used in enterprises today.

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Currently, the DLT landscape is mostly fragmented as there is no consistent standardisation among different platforms and technologies. It is not likely that there will be one ledger to rule them all (Koens and Poll 2019). Thus, existing DLT platforms operate in silos as standalone and isolated without communicating with other DLTs and legacy systems. Therefore, interoperability has become an important issue to support broad DLT adoption towards sustainable enterprise digitalisation (Hardjon, Lipton, and Pentland 2020; Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020). Subsequently, DLT interoperability which comprises an internet of DLTs, inter-DLT communication and DLT platformisation has become the trending issue. Besides, interoperability of DLTs aims to achieve trust among partners ensuring that all business stakeholders can communicate across a single platform as well as across different platforms (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020).

Interoperability is considered as a top issue for businesses interested in implementing DLT-based solutions (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020), so as not to limit their collaborative capabilities with partners which implement other vendor-locked platforms. Enterprises are interested in adopting scalable digital solutions that can develop within the enterprise and across the extended ecosystem if required (Reegu, Daud, and Alam 2021). Likewise, most enterprises intend to remain flexible in connecting or changing to different digital solutions. Concurrently, other enterprises are interested in how to make their existing infrastructures interoperable with DLT platforms, usually to send and receive data from a deployed DLT solution (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020). Evidently interoperability is one of the enterprise requirements needed for the survival and mass adoption of DLTs in improving enterprise digitalisation (Anthony Jnr and Abbas Petersen 2021; Lima 2018). The lack of interoperability amongst platforms deployed in the enterprise process may result in a decreased level in terms of quality of service and loss of financial resources (Reegu, Daud, and Alam 2021). Interoperability in enterprise today reflects the secure and seamless exchange of data digitally between authorised partners (Reegu, Daud, and Alam 2021). However, findings from the literature (Koens and Poll 2019) stated that the interoperability of DLT platforms may have an impact on the integrity of the distributed ledgers or even make digital transaction to become economically not viable.

Therefore, this study adds to the body of knowledge by examining the following research questions:

- How to achieve interoperability of DLTs with existing legacy platforms deployed for enterprise digitalisation?
- What are the factors that influence the interoperability of DLTs for enterprise digitalisation?
- What are the open challenges and possible recommendations for DLT interoperability for enterprise digitalisation?

Therefore, several enterprises are currently working to develop a mutual set of standards focused on improving data availability and interoperability, which are crucial for the survival and mass deployment of DLT as an enabler of digitalisation of enterprises (Lima 2018). To this end, over the past decade, enterprises are adopting a variety of digital solutions and tools such as enabling Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) that aim

to improve the interoperable exchange of data (Anthony Jnr 2021; Hawig et al. 2019; Masuch et al. 2020). Therefore, this study aims to provide an ideal design for a DLT-based solution for data exchange with legacy platforms. Grounded on a developed enterprise architecture framework, this study depicts how IOTA Tangle (a directed acyclic graph-based DLT) and APIs are employed to achieve an interoperable data sharing to aid digitalisation of enterprise process within the +CityxChange project (<https://cityxchange.eu/>). IOTA Tangle was selected as a supporting DLT due to its data traceability, immutability and tamper-proof attributes. IOTA Tangle provides flexibility and performance to enable a reliable environment for interoperability within enterprise process. The remainder of this article is arranged as follows: Section 2 is assigned for literature review and theoretical overview related to factors that influence the interoperability of DLTs. The method employed through an architecture, which integrates different technologies, is presented in section 3. Section 4 outlines result of a case study based on the applications of IOTA Tangle and API in the architecture for validating the potential of our approach through a digital energy marketplace scenario. Then, section 5 reveals the open challenges and recommendations for DLT interoperability. Next, section 6 is the discussion and implication of the study. Finally, section 7 outlines the conclusion, limitations and future research directions.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Interoperability for enterprise digitalisation

Karoudis and Magoulas (2018) cited Wegner (1996) and stated that interoperability is defined as the capability of two or more software components or systems to connect and exchange data, thereby overcoming differences in execution platform, interface and language. The fundamental types of interoperability to be achieved for enterprise digitalisation comprises syntactic interoperability, semantic interoperability and structural interoperability as seen in Figure 1.

Syntactic interoperability describes the packaging and transmission structures for data communication and exchange among two or more systems irrespective of the systems having different interface and programming languages (Firdaus and Rhee 2020). In DLTs, syntactic interoperability involves the ability of distributed ledgers to speak with each other based on specified communication protocols and data formats. Syntactic interoperability is also described as language interoperability as it concerns the communication and exchange of data between digital platforms at the application level (Bokolo 2022). It ensures the capability of different digital systems and applications to interpret and understand the syntax of the data in the same way (Karoudis and Magoulas 2018). Syntactic interoperability helps to resolve the lack of common data standards (i.e. conventions, dictionaries and models), which facilitate the interpretation of data across platforms deployed in an enterprise. It facilitates efficient data reusability based on a standard format different from the specified data environment (Sun et al. 2020).

On the other hand, semantic interoperability is the ability of software systems to exchange data with definite shared meaning. Semantic interoperability refers to logical interoperability as it aims to overcome the differences between digital platforms at the knowledge/meaning level. Semantic interoperability enables data to be exchanged and

Figure 1. Fundamental types of interoperability in enterprise.

understood between two or more digital platforms (Hardjono, Lipton, and Pentland 2019). Digital platforms exchange data based on pre-established, negotiated and shared meanings of information terms and expressions (Karoudis and Magoulas 2018). This is achieved by adding information (metadata) about the data (Anthony et al. 2019) and connecting each data component to a managed, shared vocabulary. In DLTs, semantic interoperability is also referred to as semantic homogeneity as it aims to achieve agreements regarding the interpretation, meaning or intended use of the same data. Lastly, structural interoperability involves the possibility of addressing the differences in digital platforms mainly at the access level by considering the APIs, deployed communication protocols, etc.

Respectively, enterprise information systems utilise different digital platforms that use different representations for similar data, for example conceptual structures and distinct syntactic, interpretations or terminologies of similar terminology. However, achieving semantic and syntactic interoperability is challenging since it requires alignment among different applications, especially in a dynamic open ecosystem environment. Presently to achieve a enterprise digitalisation, structural interoperability can be achieved by employing API as RESTful web services (Jnr et al. 2020; Karoudis and Magoulas 2018). Also, JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) can be used to ensure syntactic interoperability for serialisation. An API is simply a piece of code that governs and administers the access to a server. It also comprises the rules software developers should employ to interact with a data source, library, database, a programming language or a software tool (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020). A typical application of API for enterprise digitalisation is shown in Figure 4.

2.2. Towards DLT interoperability

DLT is simply a type of database infrastructure in which databases are linked in a distributed method across a peer-to-peer network standards and mostly managed by a consensus protocol (Carter, Shahriar, and Sneha 2019; Hawig et al. 2019). DLT is based

on cryptographic rules and is deployed by two sides (Lima et al. 2021; Szabó, Ternai, and Fodor 2022). Each member node in the distributed network has a distinctive credential and retains a duplicate copy of the ledger and participates in the collective authentication of digital transactions across different computing devices within the distributed network (Reegu, Daud, and Alam 2021). Each data transaction is validated by the consensus of most of the participants within the network (Kumar and Chand 2021). All data are encrypted and digitally signed to ensure accuracy and authenticity (Lima et al. 2021; Lu 2021). Each packet of data is referred to as a hash. Hashes are validated as accurate through the common consensus protocol employed, which varies depending on the type of DLT. When a hash has been validated, it is included to the bundle of a fixed size termed as a block. The new block is created based on the previous block and is included in the distributed ledger as seen in blockchain (Carter, Shahriar, and Sneha 2019; Xu et al. 2022). DLT has received much reputation as a promising disruptive technology that provide improved security on data sharing among different stakeholders in a decentralised manner (Belchior et al. 2021). It is seen as the key infrastructure for the next generation of digital ecosystem because the data saved are unalterable and tamper resistant. Moreover, DLTs support other characteristics, such as transparency, trustful transactions, anonymity, decentralisation, etc. by eliminating intermediaries (Firdaus and Rhee 2020; Lipton and Hardjono 2021).

Despite DLTs having several potentials, the deployment of DLTs within the enterprise process comprises 51% security attack. This is possibly the most persistent issue faced by DLT as the distributed ledger is spread out over many nodes (Malik et al. 2023). However, the fundamental problem that lies in DLT is the fact that a single user can manage a majority of the distributed network's capacity. Moreover, within the distributed nodes, there is a need to validate the transactions to manage the upkeep of DLT network based on transaction costs of miners as an incentive (Alshehri 2023). Also, the costs of transaction within the network usually get higher based on the large number of nodes involved in managing both non-incentivised and incentivised traffic. This results in reduced transaction and data storage speed across the distributed networks. Due to the rather low speeds and high transaction costs, it is mostly difficult to scale up this technology in digitalising enterprise operations (Anthony Jnr 2023c). Additionally, the landscape of DLTs is still fragmented, as existing DLT platforms are operating in silos. They are deployed as stand-alone, isolated without connecting and sharing data with other legacy platforms (Hardjon, Lipton, and Pentland 2020; Srivastava, Zhang, and Eachempati 2021). Hence, interoperability has become an important functionality that can enable broad DLT adoption facilitating cross-DLT interaction (Firdaus and Rhee 2020). Interoperability of DLT also aims to enable communication among DLT platforms without restrictions (Firdaus and Rhee 2020).

Research related to DLT interoperability was first carried out by in 2014 in the study 'pegged sidechain by Blockstream' (Back et al. 2014), where the author aimed to support cryptocurrency transactions between ledge platforms and Bitcoin (Zheng and Lu 2021). Thus, there is a need for achieving interoperability of DLT, which can occur in the following as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 depicts the interoperability of DLT, which comprises interoperability between different DLT platforms. The first interoperability cluster is DLT to DLT interoperability, which involves the exchange of digital asset and the exchange of arbitrary data. Most

enterprises that adopt DLTs may require arbitrary data exchange. The interoperability of these DLTs involves more than standardising data format across different platforms but may require employing protocols that support one DLT such as blockchain to access data from another DLT platform (Hardjono, Lipton, and Pentland 2019), as seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3 depicts an example of the concept regarding how interoperability between three DLT platforms can be achieved (Hardjono, Lipton, and Pentland 2019). As seen in Figure 3, the network nodes 'N', which are the partners or stakeholders involved in each DLT within the enterprise. Within the intradomain the 'G' is designated as local gateway ideally responsible for maintaining the distributed ledger. The intradomain aids node users to maintain distributed ledger data and validate transactions within a single business domain. Examples comprises nodes that contribute to orchestrating consensus computations and mining of nodes (Hardjono, Lipton, and Pentland 2019). Lastly, the larger 'G' denotes the inter- or cross-domain gateway, which enables administrative capabilities such as software update, hardware maintenance and trusted computing base. This allows different stakeholder groups of nodes to act mutually in the governance of DLT system. The inter-domain nodes help to address inter-domain transactions involving different DLTs that interoperate (Hardjono, Lipton, and Pentland 2019).

Practically, DLT to DLT interoperability can be achieved using simple programming capabilities on each DLT platform by employing visibly verifiable signatures for actions that require transfers or atomic swaps that complete only if partners in each DLT initiate the transaction. For instance, using Bitcoin spendable in decentralised applications such as Ethereum (dApps) (Hardjono, Lipton, and Pentland 2019; Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020). For instance, DLT to DLT interoperability entails integration between DogeCoin and Bitcoin, which are two permissionless ledgers, or Ethereum and Corda, which involve a permissionless and permissioned ledger (Koens and Poll 2019). Another example of interoperable DLT to DLT includes Cosmo network and Interledger, which aims at connecting blockchains.

Figure 2. Interoperability of DLT.

Figure 3. Interoperability between two or more DLT platforms.

Figure 4. Typical deployment of API to achieve structural interoperability in enterprise.

Interledger aims at connecting different payment networks and Cosmo network aims at supporting low-level data exchanges across different platforms (Dinh, Datta, and Ooi 2019).

Interoperability of DLT to DLT involves reading, monitoring and making decisions based on events and state data (Koens and Poll 2019). The state data comprises the series of transactions carried out at a specified point in time, whereas the event data are typically a transaction. New event is proposed when there is a new state data in the ledger. For example, suppose user A wants to exchange ownership of his/her bitcoins for user B's ether, a token saved on the Ethereum ledger. A token signifies a digital asset of some value. A potential solution is to deploy a centralised exchange, which manages the token exchange between users A and B. However, this mainly goes against the rules of

decentralisation of DLTs (Koens and Poll 2019). The second cluster entails interoperability between a DLT platform and legacy systems deployed within the enterprise.

This includes, for example, the interoperability between blockchain and a conventional banking payment application. Figure 4 shows interoperability between a DLT platform and legacy systems. It illustrates a typical application of API for enterprise digitalisation. As most DLTs such as blockchains have passive infrastructure, which makes them unable to generate a verifiable-by-others signature, data exchange is the more challenging type of interoperability to attain (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020).

As shown in Figure 4, API is deployed for structural interoperability for exchange of data by enabling IOTA Tangle to be interoperable with another digital platform. This capability permits the use of data on IOTA Tangle to affect the state changes on other digital systems deployed within the same ecosystem (Anthony Jnr et al. 2020). The third category comprises interoperability between two smart contracts within a single DLT as recommended by Koens and Poll (2019). An example of this type of DLT interoperability involves integration between Corda apps, which entails smart contracts deployed on a single Corda ledger. This article is more focused on the interoperability across DLT platforms and legacy systems as seen in Figure 4 to allow data transactions to occur seamlessly across multiple enterprise systems.

2.3. Interoperable governance of DLTs

Research related to interoperability and governance of DLT has received little attention from the academic community. However, the interoperability and governance of DLT is important as in the future DLTs may evolve to an interconnected ecosystem of independent and autonomous digital platforms with different central protocols, stakeholders and systems (Hardjono, Lipton, and Pentland 2019). Most DLTs are based on consensus mechanisms/algorithms/protocol, which ensure platform integration to achieve a single, immutable adaptation of the distributed ledger (Zuo 2021). These consensus mechanisms aid actors within the distributed network to agree on data or transactions recorded on the ledger. Several consensus algorithms adopted today in DLTs include Proof of Stake (PoS), Proof of Work (PoW), Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance (PBFT), etc. (Anthony Jnr 2023a; Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020). These consensus mechanisms are based on the types of the DLT (for instance, private, public and permissioned).

Public DLT permits a participant to be freely involved in the decision-making of ledger and it is grounded on PoW and PoS consensus protocols. In comparison, the private and permissioned DLTs are governed by a set of trustworthy users described as permissioned nodes based on consensus protocols such as PBFT (Kumar and Chand 2021). For example, general-purpose DLTs such as Ethereum, a permissionless or public DLT, permit any user to join. Conversely, another DLT named Hyperledger Fabric is a permissioned DLT, whose network nodes' identities are visible to all users (Dinh, Datta, and Ooi 2019). However, it is expected that in achieving interoperability of DLTs, a network of interconnected distributed ledger platforms with different permissions, incentive mechanisms, consensus protocols and security protocols and constraints can be integrated to form an internet of DLT. But presently, interoperability is a challenge when permissionless DLTs (which are publicly readable ledgers) interact with permissioned private-based DLTs when transactions are

executed as confidential data can be revealed, which are considered as private (Anthony Jnr, 2023b).

Also, there are issues related to legal ownership of data asset (Hardjono, Lipton, and Pentland 2019). In achieving interoperability of DLT, the concern is how can these consensus protocols be developed to support the digitalisation of enterprise operations. Therefore, there is a need for considering the governance of DLT as an important feature required for achieving cross-DLT interoperability among different permissioned and public (permissionless) DLT systems, with several platforms communicating with each other to make the actualisation of dApps more pervasive and much easier (Lima 2018). Moreover, the stakeholders of the distributed ledger networks need to specify protocols and define administrative controls over the ledger access for business liabilities and responsibilities according to their organisational needs to avoid ambiguities regarding data ownership (Hardjono, Lipton, and Pentland 2019). The situation is somewhat more complex in inter-/cross-DLT systems, which deploy a P2P network of nodes over a geographically dispersed topology where the participation of network nodes is dynamic over time.

Furthermore, adhering to the European Union (EU) General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which controls the collection, processing and storage of personal data within DLT platforms, is challenging, and this may impact interoperability of DLTs and legacy systems. The issues are related to roles and accountability on how to recognise a data controller in a permissionless DLT, anonymisation of private data and to what extent can personal data be stored in a distributed ledger (Hawig et al. 2019; Lohachab et al. 2021). Also, GDPR rights conflict with how to remove or rectify personal data, which are saved in a distributed ledger such as IOTA Tangle that is immutable. Lastly, the issue in a DLT is which user is responsible for managing and requesting the unambiguous, freely, informed and specific consent from a data subject, particularly if the data controller is not listed within the distributed network.

2.4. Related work

A few studies have explored DLT interoperability from different perspectives. Among these studies, Domalis et al. (2021) designed a conceptual interoperable and trustable decentralised approach for cross-border eGovernance and citizen-centric for dissemination of common public services. The author suggested an artificial intelligence-based solution that facilitates stakeholder to contribute towards a decentralised network for efficient service delivery and big data exchange that promotes an interoperable to be cost-effective and secure efficient services. Another study by Lima et al. (2021) implemented a mechanism for validating the immutability and integrity of data using IOTA. IOTA was employed as a supporting tool to guarantee tamper-proofing, traceability and data immutability characteristics. The authors employed a mechanism to validate the integrity of data via hash functions within IOTA network to enable a reliable ecosystem for digital health records.

Prada-Delgado et al. (2021) developed a blockchain-centric crypto-anchor system for interoperable good authentication. The study presented a platform that offers a generic approach of an object via a blockchain architecture for the system based on Hyperledger Fabric. Additionally, Firdaus and Rhee (2020) carried out a review on blockchain interoperability and possible current solutions. The researchers defined the architecture for

blockchain interoperable and provided guides on such implementations. Also, the study investigated several issues related to blockchain interoperability, applicable use cases and possible research direction. Hardjon et al. (2020) examined the interoperability of distributed systems aimed at bringing to the front the concept of interoperability, manageability and survivability of blockchain-based systems. Findings from the study presented a developed viewpoint for an interoperable blockchain architecture and further outlined some design standards that promote interoperability. Besides, Hewett et al. (2020) presented a framework to facilitate deployment of blockchain in supply chains. The authors presented different viewpoints on governance of the blockchains, which impacts the interoperability of blockchain. The study designed a blockchain interoperability layer, which is important when considering the compatibility requirements between different blockchain platforms.

Dinh et al. (2019) presented a blueprint for interoperable blockchains to support interactions among various blockchains to overcome the data standardisation challenges. The blockchains can communicate using smart contracts running in various blockchain systems. The study also discussed other issues related to cross-chain communication, access control and general cross-chain transactions. Likewise, Hardjono et al. (2019) researched on interoperability architecture within blockchain-based autonomous systems grounded on the design viewpoint of the internet architecture as the basis to ascertain key design standards. The study also highlighted some of the setbacks faced in the development of the internet architecture analogous to the development of an interoperable blockchain architecture. The objective is to design an interoperable blockchain architecture, in which common elements and standardisation are employed for the blockchain architecture to decrease development costs and improve reusability and interoperability.

Koens and Poll (2019) assessed the interoperability options for distributed ledgers. The authors described a set of important properties with which interoperability-based solutions can be assessed. Employing these identified properties, the study systematically evaluated the most common option and recognised several issues. Also, the properties are suggested to be employed in practice to evaluate interoperability solutions to determine which type of solution fits best. Karoudis and Magoulas (2018) presented a user model interoperability that aids in the sharing of learner data by employing DLT and the experience API. The author employed a peer-to-peer method for retaining and disseminating data with limited trust. The suggested approach is underpinned by the experience API standard excluding the need for a mediating body. Lima (2018) proposed an open and interoperable standard for DLTs and blockchain. The author focused on proving an understanding on how existing open standards can support global blockchain development and implementation in achieving an ecosystem for this technology.

Findings from this section review several studies that have investigated DLT interoperability. However, none of these studies investigated the interoperability, standardisation and integration of DLTs. Moreover, none of the presented studies explore how interoperability of DLTs such as IOTA Tangle can be achieved with legacy systems. Also, there are fewer studies that explored the multitude of technicality and complexities, which existed in achieving interoperable DLTs with legacy systems. Thus, the current study adds to existing body of knowledge by providing theoretical and practical insights on DLT interoperability and further presents an architecture that show how interoperability can be achieved in DLTs and legacy platforms grounded by API gateway.

3. Methodology

3.1. Theoretical background (factors that influence the interoperability of DLTs)

DLTs provide an immutable and trusted transaction employing a distributed decentralised method, where each user node possesses the same permission with an equal degree of certainty. Some DLTs allow trusted third-party platforms to store data and retrieve them in the database (Kumar and Chand 2021). Ideally, the interoperability of DLTs provides the ability to connect and disseminate data across different networks ensuring secure and seamless interoperable digital services. Currently, multiple DLTs are being developed (such as Bitcoin, Hyperledger Fabric, Ethereum, Corda, IOTA Tangle, etc.), each having distinct technological designs and protocols. Most have similar terminologies for mining node, transaction process, etc. but there is little or no interoperability among these DLT systems (Hardjono, Lipton, and Pentland 2019). Hence, several factors are needed to be considered for DLT platforms to be compatible for attaining interoperable communication (Firdaus and Rhee 2020). These factors are presented in Table 1.

3.2. DLT interoperability methods

The types of DLT interoperability are classified based on the technical viewpoint comprising cross-authentication, oracle and API gateway (Firdaus and Rhee 2020), as seen in Figure 5.

Each of the classifications of DLT interoperability illustrated in Figure 5 are described below:

3.2.1. Cross-authentication

This classification employs different techniques (notary schemes, sidechain/relay and hash-locking) to enable DLT interoperability without utilising a main trusted party except from the notary schemes. However, notary and relays schemes aid arbitrary data exchange usually required for more advanced interoperability of enterprise operations. However, the relays technique specifically is yet to be deployed to support interoperability in enterprise (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020). The cross-authentication techniques which comprise notary schemes, sidechain/relay and hash-locking are described further.

a. Notary schemes. Notary schemes are methods performed by trusted third parties called as notaries that facilitate participants on DLT platforms. The notaries implement agreement via some type of consensus protocol and also issue a digital signature that can be utilised to confirm a transaction within the distributed ledger. The notary schemes are one of the easiest approaches to attain the full suite of cross-DLT interoperability. Nevertheless, they are based on trust granted by a centralised body, which goes against the key concept of DLT, namely decentralisation. However, this approach can be appropriate in situations where a consortium can agree on a central authority to administer the notary scheme (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020). Additionally, if the adoption of DLT in the enterprise solely relies on the immutability of distributed ledgers and does not necessitate the replacing of

Table 1. Factors that influence the interoperability of DLTs.

Interoperability factors	Description
Functionalities provided	This involves what interoperable functional solutions will be offered when two or more DLTs and systems integrate (Firdaus and Rhee 2020). For example, a data can be sent to and from one distributed ledger to another distributed ledger.
Third-party reliance	DLTs aim to be decentralised, implying that there should be no reliance on external party. In some approaches employed by DLTs such as notary schemes there is mostly strong dependance on the role of third parties referred to as a set of notaries (Firdaus and Rhee 2020).
Extendibility	This involves the number of DLTs and systems that are to be integrated together for an interoperable enterprise process. This factor also involves the direction in which the distributed ledgers can be operated (one-way interoperability or two-way interoperability). For instance, BTC Relay permits Ethereum ledger to access data from Bitcoin ledger, but Bitcoin ledger lacks the appropriate scripting capability to read data from Ethereum ledger (Firdaus and Rhee 2020).
Scope	Entails how the state is to be stored once interoperability has been attained. For example, permissioned-based DLT store state based on the limited number of contributors as the state is not stored beyond the scope of available ledger contributors, in contrast to permissionless-based DLT where all users can access the state from the distributed ledger as the state is stored as public and available to all participants (Firdaus and Rhee 2020).
Scalability	Scalability refers to the allowed number of data that can be handled per second. In achieving interoperability, the processing speed may decrease as more digital platforms are integrated within the enterprise data ecosystem solution or to the ledger connecting to the solution (Jnr et al. 2021).
Existing regulations	Normally, permissioned-based DLTs are adopted by corporate organisations and thus are subject to legislation and hence must conform with stipulated rules and regulation. In comparison, permissionless-based DLTs are less bounded to these legislations. These conditions may impact the interoperability of permissioned and permissionless DLTs (Firdaus and Rhee 2020).
Governance approach	Governance of DLTs refers to the administration of the human-driven guidelines for node participants, the rules of usage that are encoded within the DLT hardware and software and the planned application of the DLT platform programmed as smart contracts (which are stored as procedures programmed on nodes) (Hardjono, Lipton, and Pentland 2019). Overall, the governance controls data ownership and business models that the enterprise can adopt for management of incentives within the DLT ecosystem (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020).
Rate of confirmation	The throughput or speed of DLT system relates to the speed taken for data confirmation and its mainly based on the size of the participating node users (Hardjono, Lipton, and Pentland 2019).
Robustness of consensus	Another critical element is the size of the node population involved in contributing to the consensus mechanism deployed, as this will impact the interoperability goal across DLTs systems.
State of permissionability	The state of DLT either permissionless or permissioned specifies the degree to which individuals can join the DLT system. The interoperability across permissioned-based DLTs poses additional issues regarding how data can be saved on the distributed ledger (Hardjono, Lipton, and Pentland 2019).
Extend of anonymity	There are two extents of anonymity that is pertinent to DLT platforms. The first relates to the anonymity of participants (i.e. anonymity of users' identity) and the second is the node anonymity of the contributors in managing transactions (e.g. user nodes involved in each consensus request) (Hardjono, Lipton, and Pentland 2019).
Security of nodes	The robustness of DLT system comprises a P2P network of user nodes and is prone to security of the distributed network. If nodes are compromised, the integrity of the DLT system degrades considerably (Hardjono, Lipton, and Pentland 2019). Also, the transparency and immutable may influence data privacy regulations (Hawig et al. 2019).
Type of update method	The update method authenticates how the distributed network achieves consensus on the distributed ledger state. This update method is stated as the consensus mechanism, which refers to Bitcoin's PoW, PoS, BFT, etc. (Koens and Poll 2019). The update method may influence the interoperability of DLTs.
Cost incurred	Transactions within DLTs may incur certain processing fee, and these fees may vary depending on the DLT platform. Also, the disparity in fees may be high that some enterprises may choose not to integrate DLTs due to high fees charged, and this may influence the interoperability across different platforms (Firdaus and Rhee 2020).

(Continued)

device using the latest versions of data from the other DLT platform. The drawback from this approach is that it is quite difficult to connect DLT platforms that do not have similar or desired characteristics. For relays to work optimally, the DLT platforms should share certain attributes comprising quick consensus and finality flexible multi-signature capability (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020).

c. Cosmos and Polkadot. To facilitate interoperability between different DLTs such as blockchain platforms, relays are usually employed on smart contracts running on a target DLT (Belchior et al. 2021). For example, Cactus implements multiple trusted third parties to issue data transactions in several DLTs (Alkadi et al. 2021). Subsequently, different DLT systems including Cosmos and Polkadot suggest the notion of cross-chain data exchange across a single relay chain and several similar chains grounded on decoherence and transaction latency to manage data transactions of multiple components of the system. Cosmos and Polkadot have been improved on this basis, improving the original DLT architecture and facilitating DLTs to exchange assets and data within a variety of heterogeneous DLTs (Lan et al. 2021). Polkadot employs a method for communicating and connecting between similar blockchains on its network, termed as Parachains. Using Parachains, Polkadot addresses the issue of both scalability and interoperability.

Furthermore, this aids in attaining optimal interoperability amongst chains, creating independent and parallel state transitions and providing shared security across connected chains without affecting decentralisation (Koens and Poll 2019). The Polkadot protocol employs two consensus of well known algorithms (PoS and Proof of Authority). Likewise, Cosmos comprises a network of internet of independent blockchains. It can be seen as a scalable blockchain ecosystem, where blockchains can communicate with one other to help improve transaction capacity and the user base (Siriweera and Naruse 2021). The Cosmos platform enables enterprises to build and connect new blockchain within the Cosmos Hub while establishing a network of interoperability. Cosmos aspires to achieve an interoperable hub where data and transactions can be easily interchanged using a bridge-hub approach to connect the Tendermint chains. In comparison with Polkadot, in Cosmos the zones manage the consensus mechanism via decentralised validators.

d. Hash-locking. Hash-locking involves setting up controls on DLT platforms that deploy similar triggers and protocols grounded on the use of the existing hash image. This technique is mainly employed to achieve DLT interoperability via cross-authentication. However, hash-locking is mostly limited in terms of functionality as it supports only exchange of digital asset. Presently, there are two typical types of hash-locking, which include the Hashed-Timelock Agreements (HTLAs) mainly for off-chain and on-chain hashed time-lock contracts (HTLCs) (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020). The HTLA is deployed as a P2P approach that is utilised for financing for several DLT platforms. The HTLC is another solution based on on-chain class of DLT-based financing that utilises time locks/hash locks to execute payment based on a specific time limit, which can also forgo the capability of receiving the payment and reverting to the sender. This approach aids fully supported bidirectional payment channels and cross-chain atomic swaps among assets on certain types of DLT platforms.

HTLA is a non-smart contract-based DLT system based mostly on off-chain applications and thus offer different integral distributed features similar to HTLC. Findings from the literature (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020) related to cross-authentication stated that several enterprises have developed alignment approaches that are at different stages of development. These are represented based on the specialised procedures described in Figure 5. Some DLT interoperability methods lay more emphasis on data transfer and therefore provide inadequate support mainly for subjective data transfer. Overall, the relay technique is well employed amongst new enterprises, whereas most DLT interoperability approaches deployed by businesses are more focused on hash-locking technique.

3.2.2. Oracles

Oracle refers to an agent or middleman that supports the dissemination of data to the DLT platform towards on-chain adoption. They achieve this by deploying smart contracts, which provide data about real-life scenario to DLT systems. These instances of data can be linked to weather, energy rates or status of flights. Data registered within the DLT platform can be utilised to forecast and predict activities. Practically, oracles are no different from other digital platforms such as smart contracts. Nevertheless, beneficial oracles are trustworthy since their management is orchestrated by a reliable partner or since they employ cryptanalytic verifications. Oracles deliver a data feed to external events. As such they are established as easy-to-implement systems. However, oracles do not create definite DLT to DLT interoperability as they are more aligned to supporting DLTs interoperable with non-DLT-based systems. Digital platforms are only as trusted and reliable as the oracles deployed by these systems (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020).

3.2.3. API gateway

API refers to a program that regulates the gateway/right to use a remote access and the policies users should adhere to in accessing a library, dataset, programming language or platform. API can be seen as a tried and tested technology and it is easy to implement to support interoperability of DLTs with legacy systems as seen in Figures 4 and 6. API gateway provides access points managed by several APIs that categorise the calls being handled by the core design to make simpler the knowledge for the users or the data retrieval procedure from a user (Anthony Jnr et al. 2020; Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020).

APIs receive many requests from clients and turn them into a single request to decrease requests from the client to the application. Therefore, enterprises may choose to deploy API to be used as an extra external layer linked to the DLT platform. However, findings from the literature suggest that deployment of APIs may not eventually guarantee data consistency across two or more DLT platforms. Overall, this study will employ this approach to achieve interoperability in DLTs and legacy systems.

3.3. Chosen method

DLT is an emerging infrastructure and there is little information available that classifies and defines frameworks/architecture that support DLT interoperability. Therefore, the enterprise architecture is employed in this research as a reference model to plan the key concerns, stakeholders, viewpoints and description into an organised solution. This

Figure 6. Modelling of DLT interoperability for sustainable enterprise digitalisation.

study employs an enterprise architecture developed in prior studies (Jnr et al. 2020, 2021) to help provide a framework to define the stakeholders, enterprises, systems, data and technological components required to achieve DLT interoperability for sustainable enterprise digitalisation. The enterprise architecture modelling based on a top-down view approach is employed to develop the architecture for DLT interoperability. ArchiMate is then employed for modelling the DLT interoperability. Based on the enterprise architecture framework, this study illustrates how IOTA Tangle DLT and APIs are employed to achieve interoperable data sharing to aid in the digitalisation of enterprise process. IOTA was chosen for its ability to support transparency, automation, cost-effectiveness and maturity. IOTA offers zero transaction fees and manages large transaction throughputs effectively.

Based on the reviewed DLT interoperability methods, several approaches can be employed to support DLT interoperability as discussed (see section 3.1). With relays, the state of one DLT is replicated within another DLT, which facilitates callers of the relay contract to validate the presence of a data transaction on the source DLT (Sober et al. 2021). However, relays have associated costs incurred since on-chain authentication is quite expensive and ledgers (blocks) must be continuously relayed. All the reviewed

approaches, except for hash-locking, mostly depend on a centralised body for validating the transactions and ensuring that the assets and data are transferred fairly. Protocols such as the Interledger protocol and the notary scheme require at least one DLT network, which instinctively trusts another entity. Although the reviewed approaches maintain the integrity of data communicated across DLTs, notary-based approaches including Polkadot and Cosmos utilise complex mechanisms to ensure integrity verification, thus making them inefficient.

Besides, all reviewed categories have limited scalability, except Polkadot and Cosmos, which directly confront this limitation with the notion of parallel blockchains. Also, other framework-independent solutions would be able to offer cross-chain communication to support DLTs such as Ethereum with Hyperledger Fabric. In theory, all approaches are independent, except for notary scheme because they depend on a specific ledger (block) header structure (Madine et al. 2021). In this study, RESTful APIs are employed to provide data from external systems as they serve as bridges between DLT platforms and external data sources. These APIs can facilitate query of data from external data sources and also re-direct data or asset state to DLT platform or smart contract. Furthermore, to ensure the integrity and authenticity of the data, 'IOTA Tangle' is employed as discussed in the next section of this paper.

3.3.1. Usefulness of IOTA tangle

As previously stated, IOTA was adopted in this study similar to a prior study (Giannaros 2021). IOTA is a public DLT developed in 2015 as a DLT that has no trading fees, mining or blocks. IOTA is a substitute to conventional blockchain architectures for DLTs that employ the directed acyclic graph (DAG) technique. DAG-based ledgers can provide many benefits over conventional blockchains, including lower transaction costs, scalability and performance. Using the DAG structured IOTA exceeded conventional DLTs, in terms of its quantum-resistant characteristics, feelessness and scalability (Sun et al. 2020). It employs machine to machine (M2M) principle and was designed particularly for the Internet of Things (IoT)-based industry using an interlinked architecture via a Tangle network. Data flow management in IOTA occurs with the exchange of masked authenticated messages (MAM) protocol, which offers an encrypted channel for secure data which guarantees that the receiver of any transaction receives data with integrity over a trusted source.

These properties make IOTA Tangle particularly well-suitable for data exchange across enterprise systems and devices. IOTA transactions are grouped, linked and stored together in a sequential chain called as Tangle as compared to blocks used by traditional blockchains. The design of Tangle allows for an authentication process that takes the form of a web structure described as a DAG instead of a connected list as is the method employed in blockchain-based DLTs. Transactions within the Tangle can get published continuously, synchronously and simultaneously. To execute a transaction within the Tangle, a user must authenticate two other transactions. Hence, the more contributors that utilise the Tangle, the more transactions are authenticated, making it extremely scalable. This validation procedure also precludes the need for financial incentives to reward members (Hawig et al. 2019). As stated by Lima et al. (2021), the IOTA community supports two public distributed networks (the

Mainnet and the Devnet), each having its own Tangle to which nodes can conduct transactions. Besides, a private node can be implemented and connected to the distributed network.

4. Results

A case scenario approach is employed as suggested by Yin (2009). Data were collected from partners involved in the +CityxChange project. The data helped to validate the layers as seen in Table 2. The collected data also provided evidence on each of the layers as seen in Figure 6. Thus, this section depicts the findings from the case scenario based on the applications of IOTA Tangle and API in the architecture for interoperability towards enterprise digitalisation.

4.1. Overview of case scenario

This case scenario illustrates how interoperability is achieved in DLT and legacy system via deployment of IOTA Tangle and APIs in enabling digital energy trading marketplace. The case scenario also depicts the use of gathered and managed data from various sources of energy assets to deploy a digital energy marketplace. The digital energy marketplace is continuously operated based on the IOTA module, which focuses on facilitating a safe data transfer and zero fee micropayments between integrated and traded applications using M2M protocol with IoT devices. The digital energy trade solution employs APIs for settling of trade and using IOTA tokens to support trading between partners. Using enterprise architecture framework that comprises seven layers, a model is designed to show how interoperability is achieved based on the digital energy marketplace use case as seen in Table 2.

4.2. Modelling of use case scenario

ArchiMate is used to describe and model the interoperability mechanisms in a logical way, while designing IT and business components for all stakeholders. The graphical representation provided by ArchiMate also helps to depict the application of enterprise architecture for sustainable digital transformation. Also, the elements and relationships utilised by ArchiMate are tailored to set modelling concepts, which are applications for denoting enterprise transformation. Hence, in this study, ArchiMate is used as the language to model the findings from the case on energy marketplace. The use case for the digital energy marketplace is shown in Figure 6, modelled in the enterprise architecture to achieve interoperability between DLTs and legacy systems.

Figure 6 depicts the deployment of IOTA Tangle and different APIs to show the application of DLT interoperability for energy marketplace trading towards enterprise digitalisation. Each of the constituents within the layers of the enterprise architecture framework shown in Figure 6 are further discussed in Table 3. The findings are based on a practical trial as part of the +CityxChange project, which involves partners from different enterprises (energy company, infrastructure company, DLT company (IOTA), electric

Table 2. Findings from case scenario on applicability of architecture layers.

Layer	Description
Context	This layer defines the needs of the enterprise and the indicators required, which may also be the key performance indicators (KPIs) of the organisation such as the adoption of DLTs to enable enterprise digitalisation.
Service	This layer entails the services to be provided by enterprises involved with a consortium. The services are mostly digital and are driven by the enterprise's goals and the KPIs, for example, services that contribute towards attaining one or more KPIs specified by the enterprise by enabling macro payment via IOTA Tangle, supporting digital contract among partners, reducing cost incurred during payment, etc.
Business	This layer describes the various enterprises' operations that are involved in providing various services. Here, the enterprises would usually be organisations that need to co-operate to provide similar service to specific clients or customers.
Application and data processing	Application and data processing layer describe the different platforms that support various digital services. These platforms may support data analysis and processing needed to provide relevant service towards digitalisation of enterprise operations.
Data space	The data space provides an outline of relevant data sources both offline and online that could be utilised by digital platforms within the enterprise to provide digital service to stakeholders. This layer is responsible for leveraging on available data such as real-time data, online data, meta-data, opening for big data markets and contracts for data utilisation.
Technologies	Technologies layer captures the different technologies that support the data sources and digital platforms deployed within the enterprise. The technologies may include hardware such as servers, energy management systems and other enabling infrastructure such as the distributed ledger infrastructure for data transactions and integrity.
Physical infrastructures	Physical infrastructures layer entails the sources that provide real-time data from IoT devices, mobile phone gadget equipment, sensors, metering devices, etc. This layer contributes to maintaining integrity and transparency of data.

vehicle rental enterprise, municipalities, real estate company, urban transport company, etc.). Overall, the partners are practitioners involved in providing digital services, which are captured in the architecture as seen in [Figure 6](#). Also, the approach performs well in terms of interoperability in providing a practical digital energy marketplace deployed in a real-world scenario: Trondheim, Norway and Limerick, Ireland (<https://cityxchange.eu/our-cities/>).

IOTA Tangle deployed with API ensures data security, authenticity and easily accessibility and immutability to data, adequate for deploying applications with transparency, accountability and trust within several enterprises that come together to trade renewable energy within the consortium. Furthermore, regarding interoperability of DLTs and legacy systems, the integration of IOTA Tangle constitutes the backbone of the energy marketplace solution, which is capable of effectively addressing the complexity of the energy trading processes and ensuring security, auditability, immutability and trustworthiness, required in enterprise operation. By combining functionalities enabled by IOTA Tangle and API, the integrated infrastructure allows all stakeholders to control their data without compromising security while achieving interoperability.

Findings from [Figure 6](#) and [Table 3](#) depict that deployment of API helps to achieve a transparent digital by default and interoperable by design ecosystem of enterprise digitalisation. The findings highlight that different technologies and data sources are deployed to be integrated on top of the API implemented with IOTA Tangle similar to prior studies (Domalis et al. 2021; Giannaros 2021; Hawig et al. 2019; Karoudis and Magoulas 2018; Lima et al. 2021, Prada-Delgado et al., 2021; Masuch et al. 2020), as illustrated in [Figure 6](#). API is responsible for managing multiple services provided by different dApps, such as the Marketplace (energy

Table 3. Findings from the case study on digital energy marketplace trading in the architecture.

Layer	Interoperability components	Description
Context	Enable scalable interoperable peer-to-peer energy trading	This layer captures the main goal of the enterprise, which is to enable a digitalised marketplace to support matching of bids in the optimum way, and communicates the decision to the involved parties via IOTA Tangle.
Service	Marketplace servicesIOTA asset module servicesIOTA asset user interface	The services that support the marketplace comprises the following:Supporting secure data authentication and integrity.Accepting demand and offers bids. Facilitating a direct payment among the consumer and producer.Accepting payments in IOTA tokens.The IOTA asset module services involve the following: Establishing the incorporation of producers and consumers)Supporting IOTA transactions by setting up buying and selling prices.Supporting holding and transfer of IOTA tokens in wallet.IOTA asset user interface comprises the following: Exchange of IOTA tokens to other currencies such as Norwegian Kroner from the wallet to a linked user account.Setting up of commodity price in IOTA tokens or other currencies
Business	Energy producersEnergy consumersInfrastructure enterpriseIOTAEnergy company/marketplace operatorsEnergy distribution company	The energy producers and energy consumers are the main actors in the energy marketplace.Infrastructure enterprise provides data on legacy systems.IOTA provides secure information on validation and payments processing.Energy company/marketplace operators aid energy marketplace design and implementation.Energy distribution company is responsible for the management of microgrid.
Application and data processing	Marketplace (energy market platform) backendIOTA asset module (prototype software solution)Marketplace to IOTA Tangle gatewayUser interface dashboardIOTA token faucetIOTA proxy module	The marketplace application facilitates a direct payment between partners. It aids direct peer-to-peer payments via IOTA digital currency. The marketplace further request payments in IOTA tokens by buyers and sellers. Overall, the marketplace supports registration, bid manager, settlement and payments and auditing.The IOTA asset integrates the IOTA wallet that processes micro payments in IOTA tokens or other currencies.Marketplace to IOTA Tangle gateway integrates to the marketplace backend IOTA tangle dataThe user interface dashboard connects to the IOTA token faucet, which is responsible for sending payment update to the digital wallet.IOTA proxy module receives and sends data to the marketplace database.Lastly, the distributed control systems send and retain data to guarantee auditability integrity and immutability of marketplace data.
Data space	Energy marketplace data	The energy marketplace data comprise all data related to the enterprise stored in IOTA Tangle. IOTA Tangle also gets data from legacy system via APIs as seen in Figure 6. The energy marketplace data also store approved bids data to the bid manager. Moreover, other demands and offers of data received from IOTA asset module are stored in the energy marketplace data.

(Continued)

Table 3. (Continued).

Layer	Interoperability components	Description
Technologies	Data and micropayment infrastructure IoT asset module (prototype hardware infrastructure) Energy management system Connection to smart grid	All data related to micropayment are received and sent to the marketplace database to guarantee data immutability integrity and auditable IoT asset module is deployed in this layer as a prototype hardware solution, which integrates to the marketplace infrastructure via WiFi or Long-Term Evolution connection. The energy management system sends IoT transactions on existing legacy systems to the IoT proxy module. Then the smart grid connects to the physical devices, IoT devices, etc. in the enterprise.
Physical infrastructures	Energy meters and sensors Physical devices	These are the physical infrastructures deployed within the enterprise to facilitate the energy marketplace for sustainable energy production and consumption. In addition, all physical and IoT assets within the enterprise premises are captured as seen in Figure 6. These devices communicate using protocols such as home area network port or equivalent.

market platform) backend, IOTA Asset Module, Asset User Interface (UI) Dashboard, etc. IOTA Tangle and API are deployed to deliver an efficient, secure and reliable data sharing, communication channels and auditing mechanisms for enterprise digitalisation. To disseminate, retrieve and store encrypted enterprise data, the MAM protocol is employed as it encrypts data (masking), validates source origin (authentication) and makes a constant data stream within the Tangle until the source stops broadcasting data (messaging).

5. Open challenges and recommendations

5.1. Open challenges for DLT interoperability in enterprises

In this digital age, interoperability is the ability of different digital platforms and applications to interchange and utilise information. It is also the ability to transmit data between two or more digital systems while consistently retaining the uniqueness and state of the data. Ideally, DLT interoperability within enterprise should aid knowledge transfer and codification, provide fairness of information and accessibility of data and adhere to common data rules (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020; Madine et al. 2021). An architecture that supports DLT interoperability composed of different DLT systems, each representing a single distributed data ledger, where by employing atomic data execution multiple heterogeneous DLT systems can connect. In such systems, data recorded in one DLT system should be referenceable, verifiable and reachable by another DLT system or legacy platform in a semantically compatible approach (Hardjono, Lipton, and Pentland 2019). However, there are several issues that impact DLTs achieving interoperability with either other DLTs or legacy systems, such as tolerance for diversification, the confirmation of atomicity, security, enhancement of efficiency and friendliness to software developers (Firdaus and Rhee 2020).

Other challenges faced by DLT interoperability comprise how to support reliable access control for smart contracts. While any access policy can possibly be deployed and enforced within a stand-alone smart contract, a good security protocol involves decoupling control policy and enforcement from definite data access (Tenorio-Fornes et al. 2021). Another issue relates to how to support common cross-DLT transactions, for example in blockchains where they are different to cross-chain deals and atomic swaps. A well-known challenge is how to facilitate communication among smart contracts, which is presently not feasible for contracts in different DLTs (Dinh, Datta, and Ooi 2019). Data standardisation is another challenge faced in achieving DLT interoperability. For collaborators to share information within or across different DLT platforms, all data must adhere to a similar data format to ensure standardisation as this helps all stakeholders to understand the information presented. However, most DLTs employ different standardised data representation, which makes DLT platforms interoperability difficult and results in different standards with diverse data attributes (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020).

Moreover, different legal frameworks are employed by DLTs across the world. Hence, it can be challenging to determine data owner across the distributed ledger network because of the decentralised characteristics of DLT platforms, which makes it difficult to specify who is legally in charge of interoperable DLTs (Wang 2021). Also, in a decentralised

setting, it may be difficult to determine which stakeholder has handled what data, when and where, and consequently to determine who is 'accountable' for it, or who administers the information or what jurisdiction pertains in disagreements and who is responsible for data integrity. Since some DLTs employed inherently different consensus mechanisms (e.g. PoW, PoS, Raft protocol, etc.) interoperability is not support by default. But DLT platforms that employ the same consensus mechanism may be interoperable. However, findings from the literature (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020) argued that even if two DLT platforms utilise the same consensus protocol, it may be complicated to synchronise data across DLT platforms with agreement about the order of the data communications.

For example, Corda and Hyperledger Fabric may both employ Raft protocol as the consensus mechanism, but each of these DLTs employ different standards regarding how data are stored, how data persist and which stakeholders contribute to the consensus mechanism. Additionally, there are proprietary modules in private-based DLTs. This is because private-based DLTs are mostly permissioned and vary greatly from public-based DLTs, particularly in terms of infrastructure constraints that may affect interoperability among DLTs. Although the private-based DLTs do not demand computing power and consume less electricity, they can also accomplish high performance in data transaction processing (Wang and Nixon 2021). Accordingly, they can be utilised in enterprise operations such as in data centres or in virtual private clouds (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020).

5.2. Recommendation for DLT interoperability in enterprises

Over the years, there have been considerable advancements to address DLT platforms' interoperability challenges. A few approaches have been employed to achieve DLT interoperability, and one such study includes the adoption of more effective consensus protocols to improve throughput and latency. This helps in the better use of available distributed network resources and enhances data processing throughput of payment transaction channels to decrease the transactions required to be processed and stored within the distributed ledger while ensuring better performance (Gabizon et al. 2020). Additionally, standards can be employed to support DLT interoperability. Standards help to create a common language compatible with different software to be designed and developed towards achieving interoperability across several platforms. Presently, there are some standards development initiatives going on globally such as ISO/TC 307 blockchain, W3C, IEEE DLT/blockchain standards, EEA, ITU-T, etc. to help achieve DLT interoperability (Lima 2018).

These types of standards focus on enforcing enabling mechanisms and crucial building components of DLT technologies, such as client interfaces, consensus algorithms, data formats, decentralised identity management requirements, etc. These standards are developed by global organisations and industrial associations/alliances with support from the end users and development community on improving interoperability of DLT platform. Hence, it is suggested that newer DLT-based standards should be developed based on existing guidelines and principles for DLT standardisation. Hence, using a common standardised data syntax and format that will be understood by almost all DLT-based systems is recommended (Hardjono, Lipton, and Pentland

2019). Another type of data standards includes HL7 FHIR and HL7 version 2, which are developed to support interoperability through uniform data structure. These standards aid digital platforms to manage and move pertinent data more rapidly. FHIR standard is built on RESTful web services and utilises modular components as resources. FHIR supports JSON and XML data formats, which are both widely used as machine readable (Carter, Shahriar, and Sneha 2019).

Furthermore, gateways can be used to facilitate DLT interoperability in enterprises. Also, for DLT interoperability peering agreements can be developed specifically for DLT interoperability and governance. Such peering agreements should incorporate clear identification of different gateways which support peering. The peering contract may include the device certificates, device status attestations, software and hardware manifest (for instance, hash of manifest), root certificates, etc. Besides, minimal trust establishment parameters and mechanisms should be specified. A peering agreement should indicate the establishment protocols and trust negotiation of parameters such as the main management protocols, the size of key parameters, standards compliance required, minimal assurance level required, etc. More importantly, the liabilities and warranties should be specified. These are similar to the DLT peering contracts (Hardjono, Lipton, and Pentland 2019).

Researchers such as Dinh et al. (2019) mentioned that Cosmos' inter-blockchain communication (IBC) and Interledger Protocol (ILP) are two of the latest alternatives to support DLT such as blockchain interoperability. ILP is mostly specific to cryptocurrencies, and it is developed to optimise the sending of payments from one blockchain to another. It is based mostly on payment channels and therefore does not generalise to other DLT applications. In comparison, IBC is developed as a more generic communication protocol, which manages data transfer, authentication and connection trustworthiness. Presently, IBC is in its early stage of development, and it requires intrusive changes to the DLT stack to be deployed as it needs to be totally integrated with the state-machine element of the DLT node.

6. Discussion and implication of study

6.1. Discussion

The rapid adoption of digital platforms such as DLTs has brought an unprecedented impact to enterprise operations. DLTs aid towards the modernisation of enterprise services towards the transformation of business process (Giannaros 2021). The adoption of DLT platforms hold great potential to help improve information exchange towards archiving open and integrated services (Hawig et al. 2019) but are faced with achieving interoperability of DLT platforms and legacy system. Interoperability aids digital systems to exchange and make use of data. It also aids different platforms to collaborate and transfer asset or information between two or more systems while ensuring the consistent state and uniqueness of the entity (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020). However, most studies on DLT applications in enterprises have focused on designs and implementation for verifying the integrity and immutability of DLTs such as blockchains. Fewer studies have shown the practical use case application of DLTs such as IOTA to support bidding and trading services within enterprise domain.

Therefore, this study aims to promote DLT interoperability towards enterprise digitalisation to enable the integration of data generated from different devices and systems deployed to support interoperability among procedures from different stakeholders. Respectively, this study explores DLT interoperability towards enterprise digitalisation. Findings from this study show how interoperability can be achieved among DLT platforms and legacy platforms based on a case study on the applications of IOTA Tangle in an enterprise architecture for buying and selling of energy, showing the potential of DLT for enterprise digitalisation. The findings were modelled using ArchiMate to illustrate how interoperability can be achieved in DLTs grounded by API standardisation that enables IOTA Tangle to communicate and share data across the enterprise network.

Findings from the literature reveal that DLT interoperability has emerged as a theme of much debate in industries. As researchers examine if DLTs can speak to each other and will enterprises get to one standard DLT that will rule all other DLTs (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020). Interoperability is key to survivability (Hardjon, Lipton, and Pentland 2020; Hardjono, Lipton, and Pentland 2019) of the DLT eco-system. Current DLT interoperability solutions emphasise on linking two permissionless distributed ledgers as permissioned-based ledgers may not want to expose their state with a permissionless ledger. Also, DLT interoperability aims to achieve integration of both permissionless and permissioned DLT systems without a third party (Hardjono, Lipton, and Pentland 2019). The findings from this study examine the potential of DLT (IOTA Tangle) for the exchange of data, by designing and developing a proof-of-concept energy marketplace system. IOTA Tangle was employed since it is a free and open-source platform that supports a reliable environment for digitalisation of enterprise services.

Besides, IOTA Tangle supports data traceability, immutability and tamper-proof attributes suitable for digital services provided by enterprises. Furthermore, this study provides an energy marketplace where prosumers can sell energy as a commodity or services supported by IOTA Tangle and API in a standardised and interoperable interaction of different platforms owned by different partners. IOTA Tangle addresses the traditional issues faced in blockchain-based platforms using DAG technique and employing MAM protocol to connect industrial equipment and devices. However, IOTA is a constantly evolving technology; it is suitable as it offers better flexibility, cost, efficiency and scalability in managing data access as compared to blockchain. Findings from this study are supported by a prior study (Lima et al. 2021), which suggest that the tamper-proof, traceability and immutability characteristics decrease the risk of irregular data processing and storage in IOTA.

Furthermore, the interoperability scene for DLT platforms is still not well developed for enterprise use. As such, most businesses adopt Ethereum and Bitcoin compared to other DLTs for interoperability between Ripple ledger and the Corda. Findings from the literature (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020) suggest that Relays have been utilised only for permissionless DLT platforms but has not been successful in establishing interoperability for DLT platforms other than Ethereum and Bitcoin. Similarly, Hedera Hashgraph lately stated that the Hedera Consensus Service appears to offer promise for DLT-to-DLT interoperability as it offers a cost-effective and fault-tolerant service, which can be achieved in any Hyperledger Fabric network developed. This study advocates for API as a technology that is widely employed to achieve DLT interoperability between 'legacy applications' and DLT platforms. Hence, API gateway largely has a high degree of

reliability and is easy to deploy for DLT interoperability. However, API solutions are in some use cases still not scalable and lead to loss of decentralisation (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020). However, due to the potential of APIs, most DLT solutions in the market today have APIs for integration with external applications and many DLT developers are working on solutions that support total interoperability with other DLT platforms. For example, DLTs such as Ethereum, Hyperledger Fabric, Corda, MultiChain, Quorum etc. deploy APIs (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020).

6.2. Research implications

Digital transformation enabled by deploying DLTs can decrease managerial burdens and improve productivity of businesses, lessening the extra cost incurred in traditional operations to increase capacity and eventually improve the overall service quality (Giannaros 2021). With industrial adoption of DLTs such as IOTA, enterprises have been able to address recurring issues of establishing incentives and standards to fully enable cross DLT interoperability. Addressing DLT interoperability can support exchange of data exchange and lessen fragmentation and need of aggregation, affecting partner's identity, consent administration and access supervision across stakeholders (StClair et al. 2020). Interoperability is essential for the survivability of digitalisation. The deployment of DLT helps to achieve reachability, referencing of transaction data within the distributed ledgers, scalability and improvement of enterprise performance. Additionally, DLT interoperability offers a medium for permissionless and permissioned DLT platforms to connect seamlessly without a third-party involvement.

Findings from this study suggest that syntactic interoperability, semantic interoperability and structural interoperability are important to achieve connectivity of digital platforms at the value level but does not guarantee it. Syntactic, semantic and structural interoperability play an important role in providing technological solutions that can help enterprises in enforcing agreements to provide semantically compatible meanings to cryptocurrencies such as coins and tokens employed in DLT system (Anthony Jnr 2022; Hardjon, Lipton, and Pentland 2020). The proposed method has interesting research implications by describing an architecture that aims to support interoperable, open, inclusive, efficient DLT and legacy platforms to support data-driven services. The findings offer implications to enterprises that collaborate towards achieving digital energy marketplace that provides a mechanism that enables bidding, selling of renewable energy and preserving trust among private and public entities involved.

In addition, the architecture enables businesses to participate and achieve a cost-effective, secure and cross-platform distributed network for data exchange and energy service delivery. More importantly, this study provides a mechanism for how enterprises can attain meaningful orchestration and integration of systems, applications and data sources to build on state-of-the-art digital technologies to address DLT interoperability requirements. This study employs enterprise architecture to model DLT interoperability with legacy systems in enterprise environment. More precisely, findings entail the use of disruptive and innovative emerging technologies, like IOTA Tangle, and the API gateway as a means for maintaining data ownership, data access and data control as seen in [Figure 6](#) to improve the trust and quality of energy data. The deployment of API standard in DLTs has been reported in the literature. However, there are fewer studies that have examined the combination of API with IOTA Tangle technology. Therefore, this study

addresses interoperability via IOTA Tangle and API. Theoretically, the advantages of integrating DLTs such as IOTA Tangle with the API could offer adaptive data-driven technologies for creating better business models in terms of interoperability.

6.3. Practical implications

In modern business environment where different partners collaborate, there is a need to achieve interoperability among different digital platforms and data sources, enabling the integrated and seamless usage of data streams (Sun et al. 2020). Likewise, a collaborative network of enterprises that uses different digital platforms is useless if data cannot be seamlessly exchanged across businesses, including retailers, manufacturers, wholesalers and logistics. However, the lack of shared meaning and interconnected data sources is a challenge faced by most DLT-based platforms. Most data from equipment, physical devices, sensor and meters, including wearable devices, are characterised by different standards that impact data integration, resulting in data silos with heterogeneous data with the potential to achieve data-driven platforms. Findings from the literature (Sun et al. 2020) pointed out that integrating data from different sources in enterprise is a challenge, which is aggravated by a lack of interoperable standard or formats in representing resources when digital technologies such as DLTs are deployed with other external systems.

However, attempts are still slow-paced to build interoperable approaches to bridge such huge data silos among DLTs and legacy platforms. Accordingly, the interoperability between the DLTs and legacy platforms in different countries is now a top priority in industries and in academia. Considering the above issues, this article introduces an enterprise architecture as a vehicle to model the actualisation of DLT interoperability between IOTA Tangle and API gateway to automate the energy marketplace operation to maintain the integrity of interactions among prosumers, enterprises and regulators. By taking advantage of emerging digital technologies, such as P2P distributed networks, this solution is based on IOTA Tangle and APIs, which interconnects with other applications responsible for ID authentication, energy trading, energy data exchange and energy transactions validation, enabling transfer of bidding to producers and consumers and finally micro-payment. The enterprise architecture modelled in ArchiMate as seen in [Figure 6](#) creates an innovative mechanism for data communication, information sharing and retrieval among centralised legacy platforms and decentralised/distributed applications (IOTA Tangle backend).

The enterprise architecture (as seen in [Figure 6](#)) creates an ecosystem with common technologies, systems and data sources that enables an interoperable environment. This approach enhances transparency, security of data exchange and integration of data dissemination in an encrypted medium which is immutable and increase trust in data retrieved by multiple actors. The IOTA Tangle by design exposes and integrates different APIs to enable interoperability with external systems. The use of API allows writing and reading operations from deployed assets, i.e. retrieving and sending data transactions via trusted channels with encrypted data using the MAM protocol. APIs help in authenticating users and in sending/retrieving data transactions to/from the IOTA Tangle to form a bridge to the distributed network. Findings from this study also show how specific authorised systems were able to connect to different APIs to interact with IOTA Tangle, which connects physical devices using the MAM protocol.

7. Conclusion, limitation and future research directions

To ensure business continuity and competitiveness, enterprises need to evolve for greater agility and productivity to meet new demands. One method to achieve this is the adoption of digital technologies such as DLTs, which are faced with interoperability issues which prevent seamless, end-to-end exchange of data between different digital platforms. Addressing DLT interoperability will aid in addressing and paving the way for enterprise digitalisation and standardisation (Hewett, van Gogh, and Palinczki 2020). Therefore, this study presents an enterprise architecture and applies it to illustrate how DLT interoperability is attained with legacy system using the public distributed ledger IOTA and APIs. Findings from this study present a case study of an energy marketplace enabled by the deployment of IOTA Tangle to achieve a mechanism to enable the interoperability of energy-related data stored in the IOTA Tangle backend. ArchiMate was employed for modelling DLT interoperability as regards the application of IOTA Tangle with API to support a digital energy marketplace platform. Using API with IOTA Tangle, data integrity and trust are enhanced in a reliable, secured and controllable manner.

IOTA offers flexibility and performance to support a reliable environment for digital energy bidding. Although the findings from this study are aligned to energy marketplace, the applicability of the architecture can be employed to other domains such as supply chain use cases, smart cities scenario, etc. The findings provide the possibility of enterprises to achieve DLT interoperability, thereby addressing fragmented DLT systems. Also, findings present prior studies that explored DLT interoperability from the literature to understand the state-of-art, strength and weakness. The main findings present the main categories of interoperability in enterprise, interoperable governance of DLTs, technical viewpoint of DLT interoperability in enterprise and factors that influence the interoperability of DLTs. Besides, findings identified several significant issues, some of which are inherent to DLT interoperability, and recommendations. Further improvements may involve extending the architecture model to consider the latest regulation and guidelines on private data processing, thus extending the architecture alignment with recent GDPR requirements. Also, future work is expected to explore how access control and data governance can be improved during the deployment of IOTA and API technology.

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